

Supplementary Information

1. Scenario parametrization

All simulations were realized with MORDRED 1.0.4. Differences to the original version are listed here: <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED/blob/main/Versions.md>.

1.1. Baseline

Suppl. Table 1 contains the main scenario parameters and their values for the *Baseline* scenario.

Parameter	Baseline scenario value
Parameters regulating migration between subsistence and world economy (β_0 , β_1)	Model default (see section 2.1 main text).
Birth rate multiplier	1
Energy intensities of production processes and final demand components (private consumption, public consumption, investment)	70% reduction in initial intensities by 2100.
Electricity mix	100% of fossil electricity replaced by renewable electricity (hydro, solar and wind power) by 2100.
Greenhouse gas emissions intensities	30% reduction in initial intensities by 2100.
Labor productivity increase	A fast increase of labor productivity in response to an increase in world average per capita consumption is assumed. Parameters are set to enable the world to reach the (higher) sectoral labor productivities of the center already at a per capita consumption 12% below the center.
Convergence in consumption	Moderate convergence through higher growth rates of the per capita consumption levels in middle- and low-income regions. Target consumption growth rate of the periphery = 3.5%. Target consumption growth rate of the semiperiphery = 3%. Target consumption growth rate of the semiperiphery = 2%. Allocation rule set to give all social classes the same consumption priority in the case of scarcity to avoid divergence.
Land related parameters	Land scarcity feedback deactivated; adaptation of model default parameters.
Climate damages (damages of capital stock due to sea level rise and extreme weather	Deactivated.

events, additional gross fixed capital formation due to sea level rise, out put loss and increase of input coefficients in the agricultural sector, labor productivity losses due to heat, loss of labor supply due to heat, loss of land, increase in land intensity for the subsistence sector)	
Climate sensitivity	Default values of the model are adapted.
Resource availability	High resource availability; fossil resources are assumed to become more costly to extract once fossil reserves have been depleted.

Suppl. Table 1: Parametrization of the Baseline scenario.

1.2. Baseline - high fertility

The only difference to the parametrization of the *Baseline* scenario is the value of the birth rate multiplier which is set to 1.2.

1.3. Damages

The only difference to the parametrization of the *Baseline* scenario is the activation of climate change damages. All damage parameters are taken from the default calibration of MORDRED.

1.4. Damages – high fertility

The only difference to the parametrization of the *Damages* scenario is the value of the birth rate multiplier which is set to 1.2.

2. Supplementary Figures

All Figures display results from the *Damages* (DM) scenario. Suppl. Figure 1 shows annual births in the center by age group. As can be seen, the increase in birth rates for the younger population groups only translates into slightly increasing annual births for the two youngest age groups.

Suppl. Figure 1: Annual births per age cohort in the center (million people).

Suppl. Figure 2 and Suppl. Figure 3 show annual births in the semiperiphery and periphery by age group. Here, birth rates in the younger age groups increase sufficiently to cause a net increase in births when all age groups are aggregated.

Suppl. Figure 2: Annual births per age cohort in the semiperiphery (million people).

Suppl. Figure 3: Annual births per age cohort in the periphery (million people).

Suppl. Figure 4 shows changes in mortality rate for one age group, representative of all age groups. Due to the climate change induced decline in economic production, the convergence of mortality rates between world regions is halted and reversed.

Suppl. Figure 4: Mortality rate for the population aged 25-29 in the center (blue line), semiperiphery (red line) and periphery (grey line).